

A series of apparent relations among fundamental physical constants

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Abstract. A series of apparent relations were derived from a hypothetical energetic system, in which a singularity state is split to two states whose probabilities differ by the geometric-constant golden-ratio φ . Among the relations is $G = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi^2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2} - h \times 10^{23} \text{ kg}^{-2} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. The Newtonian constant of gravitation, G , calculated using this expression to the sixth significant digit from the Planck constant h of an accepted exact value is $6.67430 \times 10^{-11} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}$, which matches the accepted G that was recommended by CODATA in 2018. An evaluation of this relation on the Planck scale yields an expression of energy (E_p) in the form of a harmonic mean of weighted spatial and temporal frequencies, i.e.,

$$E_p = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi}{\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{10^{10} \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ s}^2}{m_p^2 \xi_p} + \frac{10^{33} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}}{f_p} \right)}$$

where m_p , ξ_p , and f_p are the Planck mass, spatial frequency, and temporal frequency, respectively. A third relation is $h^2 \times 10^{33} \frac{\text{s}}{\text{kg m}^2} - \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi^2 h + \frac{2\pi G c q_e^2}{\alpha} \times 10^3 \left(\frac{\text{s kg}}{\text{m c}}\right)^2 = 0$, in which c is the speed of light in vacuum, and q_e is the elementary charge, and α is the fine-structure constant. In terms of h , this relation is a quadratic equation

$$\text{with the following two solutions: } h = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi^2 \pm \sqrt{\left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi^2\right]^2 - \kappa q_p^2 c^5 \times 10^{36} \frac{\text{kg s}^3}{\text{m}^4 \text{ c}^2}}}{2 \times 10^{33} \frac{\text{s}}{\text{kg m}^2}} \text{ where } \kappa = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}$$

and $q_p = \frac{q_e}{\sqrt{\alpha}}$, which are the Einstein gravitational constant in his field equations and the so-called Planck charge, respectively. One solution is the accepted Planck constant itself whereas the other solution has the significant digits of G . The arithmetic mean of these two solutions, i.e., the x -coordinate of the vertex of the parabola corresponding to the quadratic equation, equals the factor that scales f_p in the above expression of E_p , i.e., $\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi \times 10^{-10} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}$, whereas the mean of their counterparts of G corresponds to the factor that scales $m_p^2 \xi_p$, i.e., $\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi \times 10^{-33} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. A fourth relation is $|F_G| = \left(\frac{\alpha}{q_e^2} \times 10^0 \text{ C}^2\right) \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \frac{\text{s}}{\text{kg m}^2}\right] \left(\frac{hc}{2\pi}\right) \left(\frac{1}{c} \times 10^0 \frac{1}{\text{s}}\right)^2$, in which $|F_G|$ is the magnitude of gravitational force. Each of the first two multiplying components in this relation results in a unitless number that can be scaled to yield a specific amount of F_G ; the third one, $\frac{hc}{2\pi}$, is a physical constant with the units of “ $J \text{ m}$ ” or “ $N \text{ m}^2$ ”, which would relate an angular wavelength number to energy or, formulaically, curvature to $|F_G|$; and the last one, $\left(\frac{1}{c} \times 10^0 \frac{1}{\text{s}}\right)^2$, has the units of $\frac{1}{\text{m}^2}$, which are the same as those of the curvature of a surface in a three-dimensional space.

Introduction

Among the four fundamental types of physical interactions, gravitational and electromagnetic interactions are commonly experienced in daily life. At subatomic levels, gravity is generally considered to be the weakest among the four types. However, on the Planck scale, they are expected to have comparable amounts of underlying energy and become unified.

Derived from Newton's law, the gravitational potential energy (U^G) between two bodies with the masses M_1 and M_2 is given by

$$U^G = -G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r} \quad (1)$$

where G is the Newtonian constant of gravitation and r defines the distance between the mass centers of these two bodies. In Einstein's theory of general relativity, gravitation is caused by the curvature of spacetime, where each term, e.g., the Ricci curvature tensor ($R_{\mu\nu}$) that underlies the Einstein tensor ($G_{\mu\nu}$), in the field equations underlying the theory has the units of $\frac{1}{m^2}$. For reference, these units are the same as those of the Gaussian curvature (K) of a smooth surface in a three-dimensional space, which is given by the product of the principal curvatures (κ_1 and κ_2). Analogous to Newton's law, Coulomb's law states that the electrical potential energy between two interacting charges is inversely proportional to the distance between their centers.

In the Planck relation, the electromagnetic energy (E^h) of a photon is expressed as

$$E^h = h\nu \quad (2)$$

where h is Planck's constant and ν is the temporal frequency of the photon. Thus, G and h are fundamental physical constants.

Accurate physical constants are important because the quantitative predictions of theories of physics cannot be more accurate than the numerical values of the constants that the theories contain and, furthermore, accurate numerical values of these constants are necessary for testing the overall consistency and correctness of the basic theories of physics [1]. The constant h has been accurately determined to the ninth significant digit and been fixed to the generally accepted exact value of $6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}$ ($kg \ m^2 \ s^{-1}$) with zero uncertainty [2,3].

In contrast, the relative weakness of gravitational interactions and the inability to shield gravitational effects make it extremely challenging to determine G and, furthermore, there is neither definitive relationship between G and any of other fundamental physical constants, nor theoretical prediction of the G value, against which to test experimental results [4-6]. There have, however, been attempts to establish relations between G and other physical constants. For example, in a theoretical study, which relates G to h through other constants, the calculated value of G using the resulting preliminary formula is 6.79769×10^{-11} [7]. In the subsequent adjusting and refining steps, the scalars $2^{-\frac{1}{38}}$ and $2^{-\frac{1}{1.6 \times 10^5}}$ were used to numerically close the gap of 1.85% between this calculated value and the generally accepted value of G .

Experimentally, more than a dozen of G were determined in the last four decades, the values of which agree only on the first three significant digits 6.67 [4,8-23]. For higher accuracy, the Committee on Data of the International Science Council (CODATA) used a pool of 16 sets of experimental measurements of G together as the basis of the G value that they recommended in 2018. This recommended G , i.e., $6.67430 \times 10^{-11} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}$, has six significant digits, [2,24], which has since been generally accepted.

Derivation of an apparent relation between G and h from a hypothetical system

Let's suppose that a singularity state is split to two states, S_1 and S_2 , with the probabilities p_1 and p_2 , and the energy levels E_1 and E_2 defined as $E_i = U_i - F$. While U_i is the internal energy, F is the Helmholtz free energy related to the partition function Z as $F = -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln Z = -k_B T \ln Z$, in which thermodynamic β corresponds to the inverse of the product of the Boltzmann constant k_B and thermodynamic temperature T in the unit K . The mean energy of E_1 and E_2 may be expressed as their state-probability-weighted average, denoted as $\langle E \rangle$:

$$\langle E \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^{N=2} p_i E_i = p_1 E_1 + p_2 E_2 \quad (3)$$

According to the Maxwell-Boltzmann statistics, the probability of state i may be expressed as

$$p_i = e^{-\beta E_i} \quad (4)$$

and

$$E_i = -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln p_i \quad (5)$$

Then, $\langle E \rangle$ may be re-expressed as

$$\langle E \rangle = -\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{i=1}^{N=2} p_i \ln p_i \quad (6)$$

which has the form of Gibbs' entropy. For ease of communication here, $-\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} p_i \ln p_i$ is denoted simply as ζ_p (chosen for the relatively infrequent use of ζ in physics):

$$\zeta_p = -\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} p_i \ln p_i \quad (7)$$

As expected, the plot of ζ_p against p_1 is symmetric, in which $\zeta_p \rightarrow 0$ while $p_1 \rightarrow 0$ or $p_1 \rightarrow 1$, and the maximum of ζ_p has a value of $-\ln \frac{1}{2} = 0.693 \dots$ which occurs at $p_1 = 0.5$ (Figure 1A on the next page).

The amount of energy that would be yielded from such a split, i.e., a partition of a unity probability space to two portions, is evaluated against a unit of energy (E_u) that is defined here as the arithmetic average of $-U^G$ and E^h of comparable amounts, with a ratio equaling that between the significant digits of their underlying constants G and h :

$$E_u = -U^G + E^h = \frac{1}{2}(G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{33} \text{ s}^{-1}) = 6.550 \dots \times 10^{-1} J \quad (8)$$

While the exponents of the scalar value of its two components are those integers, this unit of energy is on the order of 1 J, which may be scaled to a desired amount.

Figure 1. (A) The relation between $\zeta_p = -\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} p_i \ln p_i$ and p_1 . (B) The ratio of $\langle E \rangle$ to E_u , plotted against p_1 , where $\langle E \rangle = -\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} p_i \ln p_i J$ and $E_u = -U^G + E^h = \frac{1}{2}(G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{33} \text{ s}^{-1})$. The inset shows the region from $p_1 = 0.382$ to $p_1 = 0.618$. When p_1 equals either of these two values, the ratio equals 1.000. In both A and B, p_1 is plotted from near 0 to near 1.

The ratio of $\langle E \rangle$ (Eq. 6) to E_u (Eq. 8) is evaluated under the condition of $\frac{1}{\beta} = 1 J$ for comparability. Figure 1B shows that the plot of this ratio against p_1 is also symmetric with a maximum of 1.042..., expected to occur at $p_1 = 0.5$. Intriguingly, the ratio has an apparent unity value when $p_1 = 0.382 \dots$ or $0.618 \dots$. The region demarcated by the two numbers are shown in the inset within Figure 1B. These two numbers are special in that if 0.618... corresponds to the inverse of the irrational geometric-constant golden-ratio $\varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} = 1.618 \dots$, then 0.382... corresponds to the inverse of φ^2 . The sum of these two inversed values is known to yield a unity value:

$$\frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = 1 \quad (9)$$

which is the quadratic equation used to solve the inverse of φ . For the positive root, $\frac{1}{\varphi} = 0.618 \dots$ and then $\frac{1}{\varphi^2} = 0.382 \dots$. This finding points to that under the present conditions, there are the following approximate equalities: $p_1 = \frac{1}{\varphi}$ and $p_2 = \frac{1}{\varphi^2}$ (and *vice versa*), and thus $E_2 = 2E_1$; $-\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i}$ is near the maximum of ζ_p (Eq. 7; Fig. 1A). With this pair of probabilities, the mean energy $\langle E \rangle$ is expressed as

$$\langle E_\varphi \rangle = -\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} = -\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} J = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi J = 6.650 \dots \times 10^{-1} J \quad (10)$$

which approximately equals E_u (Eq. 8).

To further check this approximate equality, the ratio of E_u to $\langle E_\varphi \rangle$ is directly calculated:

$$\frac{E_u}{\langle E_\varphi \rangle} = \frac{\frac{1}{2}(G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{33} \text{ s}^{-1})}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}} = \frac{\frac{1}{2}(0.667430 + 0.6626070) \text{ J}}{(1 + 0.3819660) \times 0.4812118 \text{ J}} = 1.00000 \quad (11)$$

This calculation is limited to the sixth significant digit by the precision of G . At this precision, the ratio has an apparent unity value. An arguably desirable implication of this finding is that G may be calculated from h that has an accepted exact value of $6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ (kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1})$ with zero uncertainty [2,3].

To calculate G , Eq. 11 is rearranged to

$$G = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2} - h \times 10^{23} \text{ kg}^{-2} \text{ m s}^{-1} \quad (12)$$

In this equation, G is related to h by the mathematical constants 1, 2, e and φ along with their physical units and associated exponential scalars [25]. For direct comparison, G is first calculated to the sixth significant digit from h (see Appendix for details of the calculation):

$$G_{\text{cal-6}} = 6.67430 \times 10^{-11} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2} \quad (13)$$

which matches the accepted $G = 6.67430 \times 10^{-11} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}$, recommended by CODATA in 2018 [2,24].

To demonstrate the resulting relation does not depend on any particular system of physical units, Eq. 11 is rearranged to

$$\frac{1}{2}(G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{33} \text{ s}^{-1}) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \quad (14)$$

and then to

$$\frac{\frac{1}{2}(G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ s}^2 + h \times 10^{33} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s})}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi} = 1 \quad (15)$$

and further to

$$\frac{\frac{1}{2}(N_G \times 10^{10} + N_h \times 10^{33})}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi} = 1 \quad (16)$$

where N_G or N_h is the numerical values of G or h , each of which includes an exponential scalar but not physical units, i.e., $N_G = 6.67430 \times 10^{-11}$ or $N_h = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}$. Because Eq. 16 contains only numbers, it should not depend on any system of units. As such, a desired system of physical units may be conferred upon this relation.

It is noteworthy that the significant digits of $\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi$ are approximately the average, or the symmetry point, of those corresponding ones of G and h , a feature that will be seen below

in different views. Thus, in Eq. 15, G and h are apparently related via the geometry-based expression $\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi$ derived from the partition of a unity probability space to $\frac{1}{\varphi}$ and $\frac{1}{\varphi^2}$ (Eqs. 9 and 10).

The term $\frac{1}{\varphi^2}$ in Eq. 9 may be expanded to a finite series plus an extra term. Then, the entire Eq. 9 may be expressed as a related finite series plus the extra term, or as an infinite series in the limit where the extra term approaches zero:

$$\frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = \frac{1}{\varphi} + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{2N+2}} = \sum_{j=0}^N \frac{1}{\varphi^{2j+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{2N+2}} = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2j+1}} \quad (17)$$

where i is a positive integer whereas j is zero or a positive integer. The final expression in Eq. 17 may be transformed to the following energetic expression [26]:

$$-\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2j+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2j+1}} = (2j + 1)E_0 \quad (18)$$

which has the form for the energy eigenvalues of the solution of the time-independent Schrödinger equation describing a quantum harmonic oscillator [27]. In this weighted natural logarithmic form, the first and last series in Eq. 17 are such related that [26]:

$$-\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} = -\frac{1}{\varphi} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2j+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2j+1}} \quad (19)$$

Thus, Eqs. 11, 12 and 15 can similarly be obtained from the latter expression by substituting $-\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} J$ in Eq. 10 with $-\frac{1}{\varphi} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2j+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2j+1}} J$.

As a further exercise, G is calculated using Eq. 12 to the ninth significant digit from all nine significant digits of h [2,3] (see Appendix for details of the calculation):

$$G_{cal-9} = 6.67429758 \times 10^{-11} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2} \quad (20)$$

It will be interesting to learn the extent to which this apparent relation between G and h does or does not hold, when a more precise and independently reproducible experimental estimate of G becomes available in the future.

Evaluation of the apparent relation between G and h through comparing Newton's law of gravitation and Coulomb's law

Henceforth, unless specified otherwise, all implicitly approximate equalities are numerically valid to the sixth significant digit limited by the precision of accepted G , or the ninth significant digit if G_{cal-9} is used (Eq. 20). In the context of Eq. 12, a comparison of Newton's law of gravitation and Coulomb's law yields some intriguing relations [28].

Derived from Coulomb's law, the electric potential energy (U^E) between two interacting charges, Q_1 and Q_2 , is expressed as

$$U^E = k_e \frac{Q_1 Q_2}{r} \quad (21)$$

where Coulomb's constant k_e is given by

$$k_e = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \quad (22)$$

in which ϵ_0 is the vacuum electric permittivity that is, in turn, determined from the fine-structure constant (α) in accordance with the relation:

$$\epsilon_0 = \frac{q_e^2}{2\alpha hc} \quad (23)$$

where q_e is the elementary charge, and c is the speed of light in vacuum, both of which have accepted exact values. Substituting Eq. 23 into Eq. 22 yields

$$k_e = \frac{\alpha hc}{2\pi q_e^2} \quad (24)$$

To compare Newton's law of gravitation and Coulomb's law, the ratio between $-U^G$ and U^E is expressed as

$$\frac{-U^G}{U^E} = \frac{G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r}}{k_e \frac{Q_1 Q_2}{r}} = \frac{G \times 10^0 \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}}{k_e \times 10^0 \text{ C}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}} \quad (25)$$

where the number 10^0 of a unity value is used as an explicit numerical "base-scalar" to separate a physical constant and the units of physical quantities. Combining Eqs. 12 and 25 leads to

$$\frac{-U^G}{U^E} = \frac{G \times 10^0 \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}}{k_e \times 10^0 \text{ C}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}} = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} - h \times 10^{23} \text{ s}^{-1}}{c^2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ kg}} \quad (26)$$

On the left side of the second equal sign in this equation, the gravitational potential energy is normalized to the electrical potential energy, whereas on its right side, the energetic expression is normalized to an amount of mass energy ($c^2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ kg}$) expressed in accordance with Einstein's mass-energy relation ($E = Mc^2$). Here, the gravitational energy can be scaled to a specific level in a manner that may be independent of the photon energy, as long as the electrical potential energy or mass energy is adjusted such that an overall equality-relation among these four components is maintained.

Substituting Eq. 24 into Eq. 26 yields

$$\frac{2\pi q_e^2 G}{\alpha ch} = \frac{1}{c^2} \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \frac{\text{s}}{\text{kg m}^2} \right] \left(\frac{m \text{ C}}{s \text{ kg}} \right)^2 \quad (27)$$

which may be re-expressed as

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi = \frac{1}{2} \left[10^3 \frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \left(\frac{q_e c}{m_p} \times 10^0 \frac{\text{kg s}}{c \text{ m}} \right)^2 + h \times 10^{33} \frac{\text{s}}{\text{kg m}^2} \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[10^3 \left(\frac{q_p c}{m_p^r} \times 10^0 \frac{kg s}{c m} \right)^2 + 2\pi \hbar \times 10^{33} \frac{s}{kg m^2} \right] \quad (28)$$

where for clarity, the units are written explicitly in the numerator and the denominator; q_p is the so-called Planck charge:

$$q_p = \frac{q_e}{\sqrt{\alpha}} \quad (29)$$

and

m_p or m_p^r is the Planck mass expressed with h or its reduced form (\hbar) as

$$m_p = \sqrt{\frac{hc}{G}} \quad \text{or} \quad m_p^r = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}} \quad (30)$$

In Eq. 28, electric charge in the unit C is normalized against q_e or q_p , mass in kg against m_p or m_p^r , speed in the unit $\frac{m}{s}$ (expressed in its inverse) against c , and action or quantum angular momentum in $\frac{kg m^2}{s}$ (also expressed in its inverse) against h or \hbar . As such, all units are cancelled out *in situ*. Thus, this equation can be expressed in the following unitless forms:

$$\frac{10^3 \frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \left(\frac{N_{q_e} N_c}{N_{m_p}} \right)^2 + 10^{33} N_h}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2} = \frac{10^3 \left(\frac{N_{q_p} N_c}{N_{m_p^r}} \right)^2 + 10^{33} (2\pi N_{\hbar})}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2} = 1 \quad (31)$$

where N_{q_e} , N_c , N_{m_p} or $N_{m_p^r}$, and N_h or N_{\hbar} represent the numerical values of the physical constants q_e , c , m_p or m_p^r , and h or \hbar , each of which includes the exponential scalar but not physical units. Because Eq. 31 contains only numbers, it does not depend on any system of units, and a chosen system can be conferred upon it.

Through comparing Eqs. 15 and 28, one sees the following formulaic relation:

$$\frac{2}{\alpha} \times 10^0 m = \frac{2G}{c^2} \left(\frac{m_p^r}{q_e} \times 10^0 \frac{c}{kg} \right)^2 \times 10^7 kg \quad (32)$$

Should $\left(\frac{m_p^r}{q_e} \times \frac{c}{kg} \right)^2 \times 10^7 kg$ be taken as the expression for a mass (M), i.e.,

$$M = \left(\frac{m_p^r}{q_e} \times \frac{c}{kg} \right)^2 \times 10^7 kg = 9.223 \dots \times 10^{28} kg \quad (33)$$

Eq. 32 would correspond to the expression of the Schwarzschild radius (r_s), which is a parameter in his solution to the field equations in Einstein's theory of general relativity. This radius defines

the event horizon of a Schwarzschild black hole generated by M in the following relation, and substituting M by what is defined in Eq. 33 yields the latter part of the relation:

$$r_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2} = \frac{2G}{c^2} \left(\frac{m_p^r}{q_e} \times \frac{c}{kg} \right)^2 \times 10^7 kg = \frac{2}{\alpha} \times 10^0 m = 274... m \quad (34)$$

In this case, $\frac{1}{\alpha}$ would equal the numerical value of $\frac{r_s}{2}$:

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} = \frac{N_{r_s}}{2} = 10^7 N_G \left(\frac{N_{m_p^r}}{N_{q_e} N_c} \right)^2 \quad (35)$$

For reference, the amount of mass defined in Eq. 33 and r_s in Eq. 34 are about one 10th of those of the sun.

Regarding Eq. 27, it may be rewritten in the form to express the magnitude of the gravitational force (F_G) such that

$$\begin{aligned} |F_G| &= G \times 10^0 \left(\frac{kg}{m} \right)^2 \\ &= \left(\frac{\alpha}{q_e^2} \times 10^0 C^2 \right) \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \frac{s}{kg m^2} \right] \left(\frac{hc}{2\pi} \right) \left(\frac{1}{c} \times 10^0 \frac{1}{s} \right)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

in which each of the first two multiplying components results in a unitless number that can be scaled to yield a specific amount of F_G ; the third component, $\frac{hc}{2\pi}$, is a constant with the units of “ $J m$ ” or “ $N m^2$ ”; and the last component, $\left(\frac{1}{c} \times 10^0 \frac{1}{s} \right)^2$, has the units of $\frac{1}{m^2}$. As such, $|F_G|$ effectively remains to be proportional to $\frac{1}{m^2}$, i.e., two multiplying $\frac{1}{m}$ units. One of these two identical units might be interpreted as that of angular wavelength number, or the inverse of wavelength, and the other as that of the inversed distance between the centers of two bodies of mass. Alternatively, the units $\frac{1}{m^2}$ might be interpreted, in terms of geometry, as the units of two-dimensional curvature of a surface in a three-dimensional space. For illustration, Eq. 36 is rearranged to

$$\left(\frac{2\pi}{hc} \right) |F_G| = \left(\frac{\sqrt{\alpha}}{q_e} \times 10^0 C \right)^2 \left[10^{-3} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi^2 - h \times 10^{30} \frac{s}{kg m^2} \right] \left(\frac{1}{c} \times 10^0 \frac{1}{s} \right)^2 \quad (37)$$

which shares the same units $\frac{1}{m^2}$ with the Einstein field equations.

In terms of h , Eq. 27 is a quadratic equation, which is put into the following more standard form [28]:

$$h^2 \times 10^{33} \frac{s}{kg m^2} - \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi^2 h + \frac{2\pi G c q_e^2}{\alpha} \times 10^3 \left(\frac{s kg}{m c} \right)^2 = 0 \quad (38)$$

whose two solutions are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 h &= \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 \pm \sqrt{\left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2\right]^2 - \frac{8\pi G c q e^2}{\alpha} \times 10^{36} \frac{kg s^3}{m^4 c^2}}}{2 \times 10^{33} \frac{s}{kg m^2}} \\
 &= \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 \pm \sqrt{\left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2\right]^2 - \kappa q p^2 c^5 \times 10^{36} \frac{kg s^3}{m^4 c^2}}}{2 \times 10^{33} \frac{s}{kg m^2}} \quad (39)
 \end{aligned}$$

where G is extended to the ninth significant digit using G_{cal-9} ; $\kappa = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}$, which is the Einstein gravitational constant in his field equations with an overall unit of the inverse of newton ($\frac{1}{N}$).

Given that the net unit of the product $q p^2 c^5 \times 10^{36} \frac{kg s^3}{m^4 c^2}$ is N , multiplying this product by κ yields a unitless value. The resulting value and that of h are related by $\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2$, which is derived from a geometric-constant-based partition of probability space (Eqs. 9 and 10), and by the scalar in the denominator.

The solution with a smaller value is the accepted Planck constant itself:

$$h = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \frac{kg m^2}{s} \quad (40)$$

whereas the hypothetical solution with a larger value, denoted as h' , is

$$h' = 6.67429758 \times 10^{-34} \frac{kg m^2}{s} \quad (41)$$

whose significant digits are the same as those of G_{cal-9} (Eq. 20), or those of accepted G after rounding to the sixth significant digit [2,24]. The mathematical validity of the two solutions can be readily checked numerically against Eq. 39 using G_{cal-9} for G , or G itself if the two solutions are rounded to the sixth significant digit.

The arithmetic mean of h and h' is calculated as

$$\frac{h+h'}{2} = \frac{6.62607015+6.67429758}{2} \times 10^{-34} \frac{kg m^2}{s} = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi \times 10^{-33} \frac{kg m^2}{s} \quad (42)$$

which equals the x -coordinate of the vertex of the parabola corresponding to the quadratic equation. Substituting the two solutions into Eq. 12 yields

$$G = 6.67429758 \times 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{kg s^2} \quad (43)$$

and

$$G' = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{kg s^2} \quad (44)$$

with

$$\frac{G+G'}{2} = \frac{6.67429758+6.62607015}{2} \times 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{kg s^2} = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi \times 10^{-10} \frac{m^3}{kg s^2} \quad (45)$$

The significant digits of $\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi$ is approximately the average or the symmetry point of those corresponding ones of not only G and h but also h and h' or G and G' . In principle, h' or G' may merely be mathematical solutions without any physical meanings or have yet-to-be-discovered ones that might be manifested by itself or an arithmetic average of h and h' or G and G' , i.e., $\frac{h+h'}{2}$ or $\frac{G+G'}{2}$.

Derivation of an apparent expression of energy on the Planck scale

Next, let's see how the symmetry feature might be manifested on the Planck scale [29]. Planck used c , G , and h to define a system of natural units including m_p (Eq. 30), l_p for length, and t_p for time:

$$l_p = \sqrt{\frac{hG}{c^3}}, \quad (46)$$

and

$$t_p = \sqrt{\frac{hG}{c^5}}. \quad (47)$$

With these units, the energy, termed the Planck energy (E_p), may be expressed in various forms:

$$E_p = m_p c^2 = h \frac{1}{t_p} = G \frac{m_p^2}{l_p} = \sqrt{\frac{hc^5}{G}} \quad (48)$$

These expressions show that on the Planck scale, the amounts of the photon energy ($E_p^h = h \frac{1}{t_p}$) and the gravitational energy ($-U_p^G = G \frac{m_p^2}{l_p}$) are equal.

Below, all physical quantities defined by the Planck units are implicitly expressed in terms of SI units, i.e., they are expressed on the Planck scale. Under this condition, an expression of energy without the explicit presence of c , G or h may be derived from Eq. 15. For operational convenience, this equation is reformatted to

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi = \frac{1}{2} \left(G \times 10^{10} \frac{kg s^2}{m^3} + h \times 10^{33} \frac{s}{kg m^2} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{G}{\zeta_G} + \frac{h}{\zeta_h} \right) = \zeta_\varphi \quad (49)$$

in which

$$\zeta_G = 10^{-10} kg^{-1} m^3 s^{-2} \quad (50)$$

and

$$\zeta_h = 10^{-33} kg m^2 s^{-1} \quad (51)$$

whereas

$$\zeta_\varphi = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi = 6.650 \dots \times 10^{-1} \quad (52)$$

First, to derive an expression of photon energy (E_p^h) on the Planck scale from Eq. 49, G is substituted with

$$G = \frac{hc}{m_p^2} \quad (53)$$

which is expressed in accordance with Eq. 30. A substitution of Eq. 53 into Eq. 49 yields

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{hc}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{h}{\zeta_h} \right) = \zeta_\varphi \quad (54)$$

rearranged to

$$h = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{c}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{1}{\zeta_h}} \quad (55)$$

To convert Eq. 55 to an expression for E_p^h , it is divided by t_p , a division that yields

$$E_p^h = \frac{h}{t_p} = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{t_p c}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{t_p}{\zeta_h}} = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{l_p}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{t_p}{\zeta_h}} \quad (56)$$

where $l_p = t_p c$.

Second, to derive an expression of the gravitational energy (U_p^G) on the Planck scale from Eq. 49, h is substituted with

$$h = \frac{m_p^2 G}{c} \quad (57)$$

which is expressed in accordance with Eq. 30. A substitution of Eq. 57 into Eq. 49 yields

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{G}{\zeta_G} + \frac{m_p^2 G}{c \zeta_h} \right) = \zeta_\varphi \quad (58)$$

rearranged to

$$G = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{1}{\zeta_G} + \frac{m_p^2}{c\zeta_h}} \quad (59)$$

To convert Eq. 59 to an expression for $-U_p^G$, it is multiplied with $\frac{m_p^2}{l_p}$, a multiplication that yields

$$-U_p^G = \frac{Gm_p^2}{l_p} = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{l_p}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{l_p}{c\zeta_h}} = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{l_p}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{t_p}{\zeta_h}} \quad (60)$$

where $t_p = \frac{l_p}{c}$.

Fulfilling the expectation that $-U_p^G = E_p^h$ (Eq. 48), the final expression for $-U_p^G$ in Eq. 60 is the same as that for E_p^h in Eq. 56 [29]. It then follows that

$$E_p = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{l_p}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{t_p}{\zeta_h}} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{l_p}{\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{t_p}{\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h}\right)} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G m_p^2 \xi_p} + \frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h f_p}\right)} = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi}{\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{10^{10} \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ s}^2}{m_p^2 \xi_p} + \frac{10^{33} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}}{f_p}\right)} \quad (61)$$

where ξ_p and f_p are the so-called Planck spatial and temporal frequencies that are formulaically derived from $\frac{1}{t_p}$ and $\frac{1}{l_p}$, respectively. Thus, $\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G m_p^2 \xi_p$ and $\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h f_p$ are complementary such that their harmonic mean equals E_p .

Based on the law of conservation of energy, and given that the amounts of photon energy and gravitational energy equal when they are expressed on the Planck scale (Eq. 48), the summation of U_p^G and E_p^h would yield $2E_p$:

$$-U_p^G + E_p^h = Gm_p^2 \xi_p + hf_p = 2E_p. \quad (62)$$

Thus, in terms of amount, E_p would equal the arithmetic mean of these two types of energy:

$$E_p = \frac{1}{2}(Gm_p^2 \xi_p + hf_p) \quad (63)$$

Numerically, G differs from h not only in the magnitude by 23 orders but also in significant digits. The multiplicative complementarity both between G and $m_p^2 \xi_p$ and between h and f_p together ensures that on the Planck scale, the amounts of the two types of energy equal (Eq. 48). Comparatively, in Eq. 61, f_p is related to energy by the hypothetical converting factor “ $\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h$ ” instead of h , whereas $m_p^2 \xi_p$ is related to energy by the hypothetical converting factor “ $\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G$ ” instead of G . Like G and h , this pair of converting factors also differ numerically by 23 orders of magnitude, which can be calculated from the ratio of the values of ζ_G and ζ_h . However, unlike G and h , they share the same significant digits of those of ζ_φ (Eq. 52).

The significant digits of $\zeta_\varphi = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi$ (Eq. 52), which is approximately the average or the symmetry point of those corresponding ones of G and h , act as the common part of the two converting factors “ $\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G$ ” and “ $\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h$ ”, conferring the same significant digits on them. As such, the product of “ $\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G$ ” ($6.650 \dots \times 10^{-11} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}$) is the modified counterpart of G ($6.674 \dots \times 10^{-11} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) whereas the product of “ $\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h$ ” ($6.650 \dots \times 10^{-34} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is the modified counterpart of h ($6.626 \dots \times 10^{-34} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$). It is noteworthy that

$$\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi \times 10^{-33} \frac{\text{kg m}^2}{\text{s}} = \frac{h+h'}{2} \quad (64)$$

which equals the x -coordinate of the vertex of the parabola corresponding to the quadratic equation in terms of h (Eqs. 38, 39 and 42) whereas

$$\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi \times 10^{-10} \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{kg s}^2} = \frac{G+G'}{2} \quad (65)$$

the latter part of which has already been given in Eq. 45.

Discussion

E_p is expressed in Eq. 61 as the harmonic mean of weighed ξ_p - and f_p -dependent components. Should these two components be expressed as their arithmetic mean in the following manner, the resulting mean energy would rise above E_p :

$$\frac{1}{2}(\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G m_p^2 \xi_p + \zeta_\varphi \zeta_h f_p) > \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G m_p^2 \xi_p} + \frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h f_p}\right)} = E_p \quad (66)$$

This is because $\zeta_G m_p^2 \xi_p < \zeta_\varphi \zeta_h f_p$, and the arithmetic mean of two unequal quantities is, by definition, greater than their harmonic mean. As it stands, under the condition that the mean energy of the system remains to equal E_p , one way to express the spatial and temporal frequency-dependent components, each by itself or as their arithmetic mean, would be a concerted transition of the converting factor “ $\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G$ ” to G and the factor “ $\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h$ ” to h so that

$$G m_p^2 \xi_p = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G m_p^2 \xi_p} + \frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h f_p}\right)} = h f_p \quad (67)$$

As such, these two components might become separated, manifesting themselves as the gravitational energy and photon energy with distinct characteristics, an imaginary forward view at the Planck time that would have elapsed since the splitting of a singularity state.

The significance of the symmetry point may be illustrated through determining the relation between w and the sum of u and v , which underlies the following serial equalities:

$$au = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{aw} + \frac{1}{bw}\right)} = bv \quad (68)$$

These equalities are intended to mimic the form of Eq. 67, and may be rearranged to

$$au = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{aw} + \frac{v}{auw}\right)} \quad (69)$$

simplified to

$$\frac{1}{2}(u + v) = w \quad (70)$$

This symmetry relation of u and v with respect to w defines the condition under which the arithmetic mean of the two components a and b , which are respectively scaled by u and v , equals the harmonic mean of a and b , which are both scaled by w .

For a backward view of the system at the Planck time, its behaviors need to be traced backward towards $t = 0$, at which it would have been in a singularity state. The amount of energy in the system, defined by $m_p c^2$, should be conserved in accordance with the law of conservation of energy. Furthermore, as the physical constants c and m_p (defined as $\sqrt{\frac{hc}{G}}$ [30], each by itself, would also remain constant. Then, at an ever shorter t , the value of the scaling factor ζ_x in the following more general form of Eq. 61 would be reduced proportionally, if the other two factors ζ_G and ζ_h , for simplicity, were left unchanged:

$$E_p = \frac{2\zeta_x}{t\left(\frac{c}{m_p^2 \zeta_G} + \frac{1}{\zeta_h}\right)} \quad (71)$$

Recall that in Eq. 61, ζ_φ , which denotes $\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi$ (Eq. 52), reflects a partition of a probability space (Eqs. 9 and 10). Thus, as t were reduced towards zero and length would also be reduced towards zero to maintain the constant c , the partition should become increasingly asymmetric towards the singularity state with the amount of energy defined conceptually in the form of mass energy as $m_p c^2$, a process that may not necessarily be continuous. The harmonic mean of the two components would become increasingly smaller than their arithmetic mean. Thus, prior to $t = t_p$ and thus $l = l_p$, the following two inequalities should persist:

$$h \frac{1}{t} > h \frac{1}{t_p} = hf_p \quad (72)$$

and

$$G \frac{m_p^2}{l} > G \frac{m_p^2}{l_p} = G m_p^2 \xi_p \quad (73)$$

Turning back to the forward view, with increasing t towards t_p , ζ_x would rise towards ζ_φ , i.e., the asymmetry of the partition of probability space should become less. Once t reached t_p , the probabilities of the two partitions would become $\frac{1}{\varphi}$ and $\frac{1}{\varphi^2}$, and ζ_x should thus reach ζ_φ whose significant digits are approximately the average of those G and h . At this symmetry point, the harmonic mean of ξ_p and f_p scaled by “ $m_p^2 \zeta_\varphi \zeta_G$ ” and “ $\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h$ ” would equal the arithmetic mean of ξ_p and f_p scaled by “ $m_p^2 G$ ” and h , respectively. The resulting two distinct types of energy could then manifest their own characteristics (Eq. 67).

Naturally, one might wonder what would be before the singularity state or after a “full evolution” following its splitting. A system that is comprised of two energetically interconnected subsystems, A and B , may be adopted to rationalize this issue. A and B would share a common volume and be coupled via an isentropic process, which is a fully reversible and involves no transfer of heat or matter between A and B . As a whole, the system would not generate any amount of net work. One might further wonder about the mathematical relation that could couple A and B . As a naïve intellectual exercise along this line, such a thermodynamic system is considered below.

At the beginning of one of continuous oscillating cycles, a subsystem, say A , is in a singularity state of a minimum volume, or zero volume in the limit, whereas the other subsystem, B , is in a maximally partitioned state, which may occupy the entire shared volume in the limit. At this point, A starts to split, which marks the beginning of its expansion phase in the cycle until it reaches a state of maximum partition. Meanwhile, B starts to departition itself, which marks the beginning of its compacting phase of the cycle until it reaches a singularity state. In this coupled process, A increasingly gains the shared volume from B .

For ease of expression, the value of the volume for the entire system is normalized to unity and is represented, in terms of probability of occupancy, by P_A and P_B for A and B , either of which may have a value of zero or unity in the limit. Symbolically, these probabilities may simply be expressed as

$$P_A = \varphi - \left(\sum_{i=0}^{N-j} \frac{1}{\varphi^{i+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^N} \right) \quad (74)$$

and

$$P_B = 1 - \left[\varphi - \left(\sum_{i=0}^{N-j} \frac{1}{\varphi^{i+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^N} \right) \right] = \frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{1}{\varphi^N} + \sum_{i=0}^{N-j} \frac{1}{\varphi^{i+1}} \quad (75)$$

in which N is an extremely large number that may approach infinity; i and j may be zero or a positive integer; note that $\varphi = 1 + \frac{1}{\varphi}$. Regardless of whether N is finite or infinite, the sum of the series $\sum_{i=0}^N \frac{1}{\varphi^{i+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^N}$ equals φ , based on the relation $\frac{1}{\varphi^m} = \frac{1}{\varphi^{m+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{m+2}}$ where m is an integer:

$$\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{i+1}} = \sum_{i=0}^N \frac{1}{\varphi^{i+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{N+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{N+2}} = \sum_{i=0}^N \frac{1}{\varphi^{i+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^N} = \varphi \quad (76)$$

The variable j demarcates individual sampling time points, which may not be linearly proportional to time. When $j = 0$, $P_A = 0$ and then $P_B = 1$. Conversely, given that N is extremely large, when $j = N$, $P_A \rightarrow 1$ and $P_B \rightarrow 0$. If N were a finite number, the entire system might act as an oscillator. However, if N were infinitely large and thus $\frac{1}{\varphi^N}$ infinitely small, the system might evolve only in one direction because the process would never completely end. Besides $\frac{1}{\varphi^{N+1}}$ or $\frac{1}{\varphi^N}$ occurring twice in a finite version of the series, each of all other terms is unique and should thus appear only in one of the two subsystems. There is no j at which $P_A = P_B$ and, consequently, the volumes of two subsystems could never be equal. Again, to be sure, the entire system would never yield any net work.

Mathematically, each φ -based term in the series may be expanded to a finite or an infinite φ -based series, and so may the resulting terms. Repeated expansions could yield a complex system of numbers, with degeneracy. Furthermore, $\ln\varphi$ in many equations derived above, such as Eqs. 15, 27, 36 and 61, as well as those shown below can be expressed as the following φ -based series [31]:

$$\ln\varphi = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{i\varphi^{2i}} \quad (77)$$

or

$$\ln\varphi = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2i\varphi^i} \quad (78)$$

in which i is a positive integer, and each φ -based term can, in turn, be expanded as just discussed (for Eq. 78 see appendix in [32]).

It is, perhaps, noteworthy that a separate derivation has led to the following approximate relation, which is valid only to the third significant digit, a condition indicated by the number of 1.00 [33]:

$$\frac{1.00}{\sqrt{10^3}} \frac{kg}{\ln\varphi \sqrt{m s K}} = \frac{m_p}{\sqrt{l_p t_p T_p}} = \frac{k}{\sqrt{Gh}} \quad (79)$$

and consequently

$$1.00 \frac{kg}{\sqrt{m s K}} = \frac{k \ln\varphi \sqrt{10^3}}{\sqrt{Gh}} \quad (80)$$

Arguably, it is sensible that the above ratio of physical units approximately equals a compound constant, in the context that geometrically averaged length (1.00 m) and time (1.00 s)

dimensions are viewed as a residence of mass (1.00 kg), which is equivalent to energy or is its source, and temperature (1.00 K) is viewed as a manifestation of energy.

Eq. 80 may be rearranged to

$$\sqrt{\left(G \times 1.00 \frac{\text{kg}^2}{\text{m}}\right) \left(h \times 1.00 \frac{1}{\text{s}}\right)} = 1.00\text{K} \times k \ln \varphi^{\sqrt{10^3}} \quad (81)$$

As such, for the conditions that the numerical values of kg , m , s and K are all 1.00, the geometric mean of gravitational energy and photon energy is equivalent to the Boltzmann entropy ($k \ln \Omega$) given by $k \ln \varphi^{\sqrt{10^3}}$. This value of $\ln \Omega = \ln \varphi^{\sqrt{10^3}}$ may be mathematically expressed in the following forms of series:

$$\ln \Omega = \ln \varphi^{\sqrt{10^3}} = \sqrt{10^3} \ln \varphi = \sqrt{10^3} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2i\varphi^i} = \sqrt{10^3} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{i\varphi^{2i}} \quad (82)$$

While all of the above discussed mathematical features regarding expansions of $\ln \varphi$ and φ or $\frac{1}{\varphi}$ may, in principle, be exploited to build a mathematical model of a physical phenomenon, system or process, excessive modeling must be avoided.

Appendix: Details of calculation of G to the ninth significant digit from h

$$G_{CODATA-2018} = 6.67430 \times 10^{-11} kg^{-1} m^3 s^{-2} \quad (83)$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{cal-9} &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi^2 \times 10^{-10} kg^{-1} m^3 s^{-2} - h \times 10^{23} kg^{-2} m s^{-1} \\ &= 13.30036773 \times 10^{-11} kg^{-1} m^3 s^{-2} - 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} kg m^2 s^{-1} \times 10^{23} kg^{-2} m s^{-1} \\ &= (13.30036773 - 6.62607015) \times 10^{-11} kg^{-1} m^3 s^{-2} \\ &= 6.67429758 \times 10^{-11} kg^{-1} m^3 s^{-2} \end{aligned} \quad (84)$$

rounded to the sixth significant digit as:

$$G_{cal-6} = 6.67430 \times 10^{-11} kg^{-1} m^3 s^{-2} \quad (85)$$

which matches $G_{CODATA-2018}$ ($6.67430 \times 10^{-11} kg^{-1} m^3 s^{-2}$).

For convenience, the quantities in Eq. 84 are listed below:

$$h = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} kg m^2 s^{-1} \quad (86)$$

$$\varphi = 1.6180339887 \quad (87)$$

$$\varphi^2 = 2.6180339887 \quad (88)$$

$$\frac{1}{\varphi^2} = 0.38196601125 \quad (89)$$

$$\ln\varphi = 0.48121182506 \quad (90)$$

$$\ln\varphi^2 = 0.96242365012 \quad (91)$$

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi^2 \times 10 = 13.30036773 \quad (92)$$

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